

THE DATE OF APARĀJITAPṚCCHĀ

By

M. P. VORA, Porbandar

and

M. A. DHANKY, Junagadh

Aparājitaṇṇchā, ascribed to Bhuvanadeva or Viśvkarmā is one of the few and most valuable texts on the *Nāgara* school of architecture ; since the text was available in printed form only in 1950,¹ its use in the comparative study of temple architecture, and in fact the thorough applicability of the canons it advocates to actual monuments are slowly being realized when fresh interest in the mediaeval temple architecture is being evinced from several quarters. The full appreciation of this text will no doubt lift it from the relatively little known and semi obscure state to an exalted status and will be a much consulted text after its critical edition is made available.

The very first perusal of this text leaves three indelible impressions on the mind of the reader.

(1) While many things in the text are just unimportant puranic summaries practically irrelevant with the main theme, when it comes to the point, what it treats is extremely useful to the students of architecture since herein one finds cogent and almost perfectly detailed statements about the canons of architecture related to the *Nāgara* school.

(2) It is a text which purports to deal with temples of highly evolved type and nowhere there is any portion which is older both in phraseology or contents. Consequently, its composition must have been somewhere when the art of temple building was passing, or just passed its meridian.

(3) Although it mentions several styles of architecture and even dwells, rather succinctly, on all of them, in the main, it purports to deal with the temples that were once constructed in the region of Gujarat. This regional limitation is reflected by the fact that its canons are more distinctly applicable to the mediaeval temples of Gujarat rather than to any other branch of the great *Nāgara* school of architecture. Further corroboration is available from the fact that Sompurā Śilpins, the hereditary architects who construct religious edifices in Gujarat almost always consult *Aparājitaṇṇchā* besides other texts such as *Kṣirārṇava*, *Dīpārṇava*, *Vṛkṣārṇava*, and *Prāsādamaṇḍana* all of which are again the texts which are distinctly applicable to the temples of Gujarat. Later

¹ The text has been published by Oriental Institute, Baroda.

Gujarati temple architecture although plain and decadent, still conform and follow earlier canons as depicted in these texts including *Aparājitaṣṭcchā*.

The question as to the date of the composition of this important text is one of vital importance since that would bring the text to a proper chronological perspective for comparing with other texts dealing with the same subject.

Sri P. A. Mankad who edited this valuable text has discussed this problem at length and before we proceed to the point we may dwell on the question as to the authorship of the text and its title associations.

Sri P. A. Mankad explains these by following statements :—

(1) “ *Aparājitaṣṭcchā*, literally, “ the questionnaire framed by Aparājita ” is an exposition, by the comparative method of the principles and practice of the science of *Vāstu* by Viśvakarman who solves a series of questions put to him by Aparājita, the youngest of his Mānasa sons. ”

(2) “ Four kings with the names of Aparājita appear to have flourished between 661 and 1161 A.D. in different parts of India. ” The last one with name “ Aparājita whose another name is Devapāla is the son of Mūladeva (1161 A.D.) (Vide Indian Antiquary, Vol. XV, P. 202). ”

(3) “ Hemādri wrote a voluminous *nibandha* work called *Caturvargacintāmaṇi* consisting of five *khaṇḍas*, viz. *Vṛta*, *dāna*, *tīrtha*, *mokṣa* and *pariśeṣa*. It is both in *dāna* and *pariśeṣa khaṇḍas* that Hemādri has noticed *Aparājitaṣṭcchā*. This fact helps to determine conclusively the lower limit of *Aparājitaṣṭcchā* i.e. 1260-1309 A.D. or roughly the latter half of thirteenth century A.D.”²

(4) A close study of *Smarāṅganāsūtradhāra* and *Aparājitaṣṭcchā* with respect to the subject matter led Sri P. A. Mankad to conclude that S.S. is decidedly anterior to A. P. which may safely be taken to the 12th century A.D.

(5) “ Further from certain affinity in the subject matter *Aparājitaṣṭcchā* is presumed to be contemporaneous with *Mānasollāsa* of Someśvaradeva.”

(6) “ If this position is tenable, it is the fourth Aparājita, son of Mūladeva, who may have, if at all, any hand in the composition of *Aparājitaṣṭcchā*.”

We may now examine the possibility if the last mentioned postulate may or may not have any validity.

(1) *Aparājitaṣṭcchā* refers to three previous works by the name *Jayaṣṭcchā*, *Vijayaṣṭcchā* and *Siddhārthaṣṭcchā*, all written in the form of dialogue between Viśvakarmā and Jaya, Vijaya and Siddhārtha respectively.³

² Hemādri had been the Finance Minister of the Yādava King Mahādeva (1260-71 A.D.) and his successor Rāmacandra (1271-1309 A.D.). The information is given by Sri P. A. Mankad in his preface of *Aparājitaṣṭcchā* of *Bhuvanadeva*, page ix. He apparently based his information on R. G. Bhandarkar’s “ Early History of the Deccan ”.

³ A.P. chapter 34.

(2) *Jayapṛcchā* dealt with the construction of buildings, palaces, cities, forts, moats, gateways, etc., while *Vijayapṛcchā* treated music and musical instruments as also dancing in its various aspects. *Siddhārthapṛcchā* had its subject matter the science of phonetics, mathematics, astrology, lxicography, grammer, prosody, etc.

(3) To the real unknown author of *Aparājitaṛcchā* who chose to write on the subject of architecture, following the prevailing tradition it was left not only to ascribe the text to Viśvakarmā but also to step in the foot-steps of his predecessors by writing the text in the dialogue form. And for him whom now to choose as the seeker of knowledge but Aparājita ?

(4) That after, Jaya, Vijaya and Siddhārtha, Aparājita should logically follow the selection is evident from some parallelism found in other fields also. The five supreme celestial residences according to Swetāmber Jain texts are Vijaya, Vijayanta, Jayanta, Aparājita and Sarvārthasiddha.⁴

(5) In our opinion this is the Indian way of thinking and naming; and to our mind, Sri P. A. Mankad's first explanation postulating Aparājita, the youngest conceptual son of Viśvakarmā as framing the questions sounds more plausible and in keeping with the tradition. That such was the intention of the original author is indirectly supported by the following statement made by Aparājita at the end of Chapter 34.

*‘ Asmaccitte praboddhavyam Jayāya pṛcchate ca yat,
Vijayaśca Siddārthaśca pṛcchāyām yattathaitayoh;
Bhavān puṣpakamāhūya proktavān yadanugrahāt
Pūrvam sarvam prasādena kathayasva jagatpate.*

As for the date of the text, however, more thorough and conclusive evidences are needed by critically examining the contents of the text itself. The literary aspect that can be used as internal evidence for fixing the upper and lower limits of the text have been, of course, dealt with by Sri P. A. Mankad. What we propose now is to use the cononical portion itself for dating by comparing its injunctions with the extant monuments themselves in Gujarat region.

This portion of the text, as has already been remarked deals with a style of architecture which is at once highly evolved and sophisticated in the extreme. That such one was in vogue during the glorious regime of the Caulukyias of Gujarat is unequivocally attested by the architectural remains of this period. But the crux of the point is this. To which particular phase of the Caulukyian architecture these canons are applicable? Is it the earlier phase when the ornate style is still in the making? Is it in the middle phase when the style

⁴ Prajñāpanā Sūtra, Anuyogadwāra Sūtra, and Tattvārtha Sūtra of Umā-swāti.

reaches its culmination? Or, is it just when it entered into the vista of decadence? The answer to this question would surely bring the date of the text into sharper focus. The answer can be got by comparing the textual prescriptions with the actual monuments.

(1) Chapters 123 and 124 prescribe the following mouldings for the *pīṭha* (basement) of the temple, viz., *Bhittas* (one, two or three in number), *jādyakumbha* *Karṇikā*, *antarapatra*, *grāspatti*, *gajathara*, *vājithara* (i.e. *aśvathara*), and *narathara*. While *bhittas* and *jādyakumbha* occur from at least the end of the 8th century (e.g. temples of Roda and old Temple at Thān),⁵ and *grāspatti* and *karṇikā* are available from middle of tenth century onwards (e.g. Kotai Temple in Kutch),⁶ *gajathara* and *narathara* can be seen from early eleventh century onwards only. *Vājithara* on the other hand is reported from still later temples. It occurs in the very largest 'Meru' type of temples only in Gujarat. It was there at Somanāth (A.D. 1169). It also, according to tradition, existed at Rudramahālaya in Siddhapur (about A.D. 1140).

(2) Chapter 127 deals with the wall members. These are *khuraka*, *kumbhaka*, *kalaśa*, *kāpotāli*, *mañcikā*, *jaṅgha*, *udgama*, *bharanī*, *śiravatti* and *kutachādyā*. Out of these members, *mañcikā*, *śiravatti* and *kutachādyā* never occur before the beginning of eleventh century. *Kumbhaka* is prescribed to have niched figures on the face and foliage on the shoulders. Such type of *kumbhaka* is not known before the middle of eleventh century. For instance, it is first found on the Nilakanth Mahadeva Temple at Sunak. *Kalaśa* is prescribed to be decorated with jewelled patterns the kind of which again appears for the first time on the last named temple. The round type of *bharanī* with suspended foliage as per prescription is again available from early eleventh cen-

⁵ The close resemblance of these temples to the Pratihāra temples at Osian, Sun Temple at Chitor, etc. attributable stylistically to the end of 8th or the beginning of 9th century is an important factor in dating the former temples. There are other stylistic considerations such as the figure sculptures, decorative ornaments, the type of *Nāgara* śikhara etc. stand mid-way between the Maitraka temples of Saurāṣṭra and the earliest Solanki temples in Gujarat.

⁶ Kotāi temple in Kutch is stylistically a very close parallel of Mahavīra Temple at Osian (956 A.D.), Ambikā Temple at Āhār, (956 A.D.) and Lakṣmaṇa Temple at Khajuraho (954 A.D.). The workmanship of the figure sculptures and decorative details of the temple in question are more vigorous and superior to the earliest Solanki Monuments of Gujarat. On the other hand certain advances that we see in the Solanki temples are absent here, although it is more advanced than temples at Rodā and Thān. The form of *Karṇikā* itself is bold, roundish, and not knife-edged as we see in the Solanki Temples.

ture examples and thenceforth only. The tenth century temples have square *bharanīs*, often double, but without the hanging leaves at the extremities.

(3) The śikhara types treated in A.P. are from the simplest to the highly evolved types and fall into three categories.

(a) Morphological types such as *Phānsanā*, and *Valabhi* in the first instance can occur throughout India with regional peculiarities.⁷

(b) *Bhūmija*, *Vimāna-Nagara*, *Varāṭa*, *Vairājya*, *Vimānapuṣṭaka*, *Drāviḍa* etc., out of which *Bhūmija* and *Drāviḍa* are both morphological and provincial.⁸

(c) Purely provincial *Nāgara* types such as *kesarādi*, *Śrīdharādi*, *Suralārvādi*, *Sāgaratilakādi* and *Meru* types of various specifications typical of Gujarat proper and to some extent Rājasthān area from 12th century onwards.

Out of these, the first two, viz. (a) and (b) show vast knowledge and acquaintance with various regional types of India, the knowledge of the original author may have been based on the previous facts as well as the contemporary regional practices as known to him. As for (c), he seems to have attempted to bring into his fold all the guild traditions which seem to be prevalent in provincial Gujarat in his time. The differences between the guilds themselves are not stylistic but of mathematical manipulations. Existence of several guilds with varying mathematical traditions for the same style proves the culmination of the style, not the beginning of it. In fact, *Kasarādi* tradition represents the

⁷ *Phānsanā* types occur as covering generally the roof of the Maṇḍapas of the temples in Gujarat such as at Trinetreśvara temple near Thān, Kotāi temple in Kutch, etc.; Mahāvīra Temple at Osian, Ambikā Temple at Ahār, etc. in Rajasthan; Mālādevi temple at Gyrapur, and Lakṣmaṇa Temple, Pārśvanātha temple, and Viśvanātha Temple at Khajuraho in Central India; Mukteśvara Temple, Rājā-Rāṇī Temple, Liṅgarāja Temple, Ananta Vāsudeva Temple, and Puri and Koṅāraka Temples in Orissa. Variations of details do occur amongst all these instances. But the primary morphic character of all these instances reflect the *Phānsanā* form.

The *Valabhi* or *Gajapṛstha* type having a rectangular plan and a keel roof shape with gable ends occur at Teli-kā mandir Gwalior, Jageswar Temple at Kumaon, Vaital Temple at Bhuvaneśvara and Bhīma's Ratha and Sahadeva's Ratha at Mahābalipuram. The *Valabhi* types though rather of rare occurrence, still has a wide regional distribution.

⁸ *Bhūmija* type of temples occur in Mālvā and the Deccan such as we see at Udayapur, Nemwar, Un, Ramgadh, Ambarnath, Sinnar, Balsame, etc. Very late instances occur in Gujarat, Rajasthan, and the Chandel country, as aberrations, and are in fact, extremely rare in these regions.

The Dravid types are confined to the southern countries only.

primary series of shikhar types arrived at by simple mathematical addition. This series is used in building up the more complicated secondary series such as *Śrīdharādi*. Finally, tertiary and highly complicated types are seen in the *Meru* types of temples. While S. S. does deal with the grand *Meru* types, those specified in A. P. are evidently more evolved and grander in conception. Such a state is possible when both mathematical and engineering competence reached their zenith. Surviving examples show that *Meru* types were in abeyance from early twelfth century, the three notable examples were *Rudramahālaya* at *Siddhapur*, *Ajitanāth Temple* at *Taraṅgā* and the *Temple of Somanātha* at *Prabhāsa-Pāṭaṇa*. One would even wonder whether several of the complicated types did not show the mathematical possibilities rather than actual practice.

(4) The types of *Maṇḍapas* and the details of these as described in A.P. reveal that from the simplest four pillared porch (*Prāgrīva*) to many pillared hypostyle halls are known, the like of the latter one encounters from eleventh century onwards. Several of these, of course, indicate mathematical possibility inevitable thanks to the ancient way of building formulae by arithmetical additions.

(5) The pot-and-foilage (*Ghaṭa pallava*) type of pilasters mentioned in A. P. are practically absent after the end of 12th Century :

(6) The pillar types also represent the simple square (*Rucaka*) square with off-sets (*Bhadra*), square with recesses (*Vardhamāna*), octagonal (*Aṣṭāsra*) and octagonal with corners (*Swastika*). Out of these the octagonal type is available from early 11th century onwards and the *Swastika* type is noticeable in early 13th century only.

(7) The subjects of ceilings (*Vitāna Vidhāna*) as discussed in A.P. is amazingly complicated and looking at the fact that most of the intricate types occur not before early eleventh century, even theoretically it could not have been possible to anticipate such a development at an earlier date. Many of the permutations and combinations described there have purely theoretical value and actual instances never follow several of the manipulations which are quite queer if not possible. While the ceilings of Gujarat temples exhibit great number of varieties which can be brought within the compass of the definitions given by A.P., it is still doubtful whether all the odd eleven hundred and fifteen types calculated out by A.P., ever found expression in reality. But it does show a master mind who could summon forth all the developed forms for exploring the possible computations. This could have been possible only when both art and science of architecture were just passing or have just passed the acme of maturity. In fact, the subject of ceilings betrays a greater and more advanced knowledge on the part of A.P. than S.S. This is not because that the

treatment is more succinct in S.S. but by what is elicited by more number of varieties known to A.P. by virtue of its composition at a later stage.

(8) For covering the roofs of the Maṇḍapas, A.P. specifies the rules and forms leading to the constructions of the ornate 'Samvaraṇā' consisting of cornices supporting bell members of proportionate sizes on a strict mathematical plan. *Samvaraṇā* first appears in the early eleventh century both in Gujarat and Rajasthan on one hand and central India on the other. Prior to that a pyramidal roof in diminishing tiers decorated with chaitya arches (Phāsanā) were in abeyance.

(9) Lastly, the iconography of the Dikpāla figures where four hands, each one bearing a separate emblem, have been prescribed is a practice observed only from the beginning of early 11th century. Deviations in the matter of number of hands attributes and the vehicles of the Dikpālas on tenth century temples are many. The closest agreement in the iconography of Dikpāla figures as they occur on the monuments with the injunctions of A.P. is obvious more especially from the end of 12th century in Gujarat.

A review of all these points would place early eleventh century as the uppermost limit for the composition of this text. It should be remembered that early eleventh century still represents a mobile phase when a given temple does not answer all the necessary specifications with a regularity that is observable in subsequent temples. The style was still in a crucible and at this very moment it need not be expected that the canonical work should take shape. The text, therefore, could not have been composed right in the early eleventh century since sufficient time must have elapsed for the consolidation and crystallization of the practices themselves arrived at through experimentations by various guilds the outcome of which is embodied in A.P. The supermost limit, if this should be set, would be the end, not the beginning of 11th century. As for the lower limit, we have to refer to the probable time of the composition of *Caturvargacintāmaṇi* by Hemādri. He could have hardly written his work at the fag end of his life when the Deccan faced political disasters at the hands of Muslims. The work need not have been written in Rāmacandra's time at all. The latest date for the work can be the third quarter of 13th century when peace and prosperity prevailed in the region. We have also to consider the circumstantial inferences arising from this. When Hemadri mentioned *Aparājitaṭṭcchā*, the text should have been in circulation and must have come to be recognized as an authoritative work on architecture. This could not have been the case if A.P. was a freshly written text only slightly anterior in time to C.C. The lower limit for the composition of A.P. should, therefore, be shifted up to say, at least the beginning of thirteenth century.

We can, however, be still precise in our dating if we regard these points more closely.

(1) The minor parts of the mouldings of a basement or the wall members of the temple and the gross and subtle measurements of them come very close and conform to the injunctions of A.P. in the examples of 12th century Gujarat.

(2) The *Aśvathara* moulding, the *Meru* types of temples and some of the peculiar details of the iconography of the Dikpāla figures such as Vāyu and Yama appear exclusively in 12th century.

These facts impel us to bring the date of the text to 12th century. While it is true that many architectural features described in A.P. first appeared in the early 11th century, their recurrence in 12th and subsequent centuries only prove the persistence of feature but with the difference that the strength of their forms and quality of carving had deteriorated. Now since the text itself does not expound the qualitative aspect of the mouldings, figure sculptures and decorative designs, we have to infer this from field studies and use the metrical aspect only, the latter being precisely stated in many cases in A.P. In case of A.P. therefore, practice has preceded the theory beyond any suspicion. The work as a whole seems to have been written by a single person and except for the borrowings or quotations his own way of treating technical subjects still has a pretension of certain individualism and coherence of thought.

The later architects, it seems, after the composition of A.P. and its sister texts, eventually lost originality and insight and mechanically followed the textual injunctions. To add to their misfortune, they were progressively losing the hereditary knowledge of the unwritten keys and subtleties on the architectural side on one hand and refinement in carving in all its aspects on the other. All these factors contributed to the degeneration of the style even when patronizing of the architects was always an unbroken affair in Gujarat. From 14th century onwards the architectural productions though often reflecting some of the mathematical formulae of A.P., look more like caricatures and inorganic if not inordinate piles.

Returning to our problem it remains clear that while S. S. does seem to be earlier than A.P., the mere fact does not bring forth the point as to how much later the latter text ought to have been unless specific reasons are stated. These have not been stated by Sri P. A. Mankad, and his dating of the text receives justification only in light of the facts expounded in the foregoing and these facts even compass the date into more precise and narrow limit, say, the latter half of the 12th century as the most probable period of its composition.
